

SYSTEMATIC STUDY OF ACCIDENTS IN SPORTS ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *In this article, the creation of a modern and effective system of occupational safety management in sports and injury prevention in sports is of great importance for the general health of the population. It is shown that it is necessary to develop and implement measures to protect against sports injuries and occupational diseases. Athletes must be able to avoid dangerous situations that lead to injuries and be able to avoid injury-prone movements of an athlete with exceptional dexterity. The article presents the results of a study of the causes and conditions of musculoskeletal injuries in athletes involved in various sports, using questionnaires and statistical analysis methods. Pay special attention to the fact that the causes of athletes' injuries depend on the training location.*

Keywords: *occupational safety, sports, athletes, injury, accident, sports, overwork, hall, games, injuries.*

INTRODUCTION. In all types of sports associated with physical movement, the registration, study, and recording of accidents—as well as the deep analysis of their causes—enable the development, implementation, and funding of preventive and mitigation measures. Additionally, such an approach allows for forecasting the required amount of insurance funds.

Alongside the development of sports in Uzbekistan, legal and regulatory-technical documents have been created and implemented to regulate the procedures for investigating accidents involving individuals engaged in professional and amateur sports, including those occurring during training sessions in sports education institutions. These documents cover the procedures for examining injuries and registering accident data.

However, the current documents implemented for recording and analyzing accidents in sports practice do not require detailed classification of such incidents. This lack of specification leads to various ambiguities and significantly reduces the quality of organizational, technical, and sanitary-hygienic measures aimed at preventing accidents and minimizing their consequences. Furthermore, it creates numerous problems when registering or documenting insurance claims.

In the analysis of accidents in physical education and sports, mainly retrospective methods are used. These include grouping, statistical (coefficient-based), monographic, topographic, and economic methods. All these are retrospective in nature, meaning they only allow for the study of past or already recorded incidents.

There is currently no unified procedure in each educational institution for officially registering and accounting for accidents during physical education or sports training sessions and competitions across all types of sports. Key factors such as the age, gender, experience, and athletic qualification of the injured, as well as the specific sport discipline—whether in general secondary schools, specialized sports schools, sports federations and clubs, youth sports, Olympic sports, or

elite sports—are not systematically recorded. As a result, there is no clear visibility into the causes of injuries or the ability to accurately forecast related conditions by sport type.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. In order to shape a physically healthy, intellectually developed, and culturally refined population, the Republic of Uzbekistan has defined key strategic priorities aimed at enhancing public knowledge and competence in the field of physical education and sports. One of the core objectives is to introduce innovative forms and methods into the selection (screening) process for talented athletes and to implement a comprehensive reform of the physical education and sports system by 2025, including the following directions [1]:

- Increasing the proportion of the population regularly engaging in physical activity and sports to 33%, and raising the percentage of youth involved in sports organizations and institutions to 20%;

- Gradually increasing the number of qualified personnel (especially those with higher education degrees) in state sports education institutions to reach 80%;

- Developing and implementing an efficient and transparent four-stage talent selection system (organization–district (city)–regional–national level) for identifying promising young athletes at the local level;

- Conducting “Children’s Sports Games” among students of sports schools under the Ministry of Sports to identify talented youth and create a reserve for national teams, and organizing “Student Sports Games” among university students to encourage consistent sports participation [2];

- Promoting physical education among a wide range of the population, including general education school students, vocational and higher education students, by developing and conducting events such as the “General School Sports Festival” and the “Physically Fit Institution” competition at district/city, regional, and national levels. Additionally, introducing nominations for the best physically prepared general education school, vocational, and higher education institutions;

- Since 2020, organizing major international events such as the “Tashkent Marathon,” “Save Aral” eco-marathon, and competitions in auto rally and motocross to promote the development of sports tourism;

- Introducing a nationwide fitness testing program called “Physical Fitness Level” to assess and encourage physical preparedness among all segments of the population;

- Establishing scientific-complex laboratories for national teams in various sports, integrating advanced innovative technologies into training, and ensuring effective medical and pharmacological support in the sports sector;

- Implementing a system of comprehensive and regular medical examinations for members of regional youth teams (under 18) at regional multidisciplinary pediatric departments, and for older athletes at district (city) central polyclinics [3].

In short, sports competitions held on a national scale play an important role in motivating athletes to establish themselves internationally. However, it should not be overlooked that injuries sustained during these events often cause significant discomfort and difficulties for athletes [4].

The number of sports-related injuries is steadily increasing and has now reached an alarming level [5]. Globally, sports injuries account for 10–17% of all reported injuries. In the United States, for example, sports injuries represent 16% of all injuries among children and adolescents, while transportation-related injuries account for 7.1% [6]. More than 50% of all

injuries involve the limbs. Ankle sprains are the most common injury across all sports, making up 15% of total injuries. The incidence of contusions and ligament injuries—particularly of the anterior cruciate ligament—has shown a marked increase in recent years, with an average annual rise of 7.0% and 1.3%, respectively. American football has the highest injury rate, with 9.6 injuries per 1,000 training sessions and 35.9 injuries per 1,000 competitive events [7].

Injuries can vary widely—from bruises to fractures—and all are classified as trauma. They are categorized based on type, severity, and location. The distribution of injuries by type of sport presents particular interest. According to V.K. Dobrovolsky and V.A. Trofimov, 91.1% of all injuries are classified as mild, 7.8% as moderate, and 1.1% as severe [8].

RESULTS. In examining the etiology of sports injuries, experts unanimously agree that most injuries result from errors in the organization of the training process. For example, 60% of running-related injuries and nearly half of all fatigue complaints among runners are directly linked to training mistakes. Such errors lead to localized muscle overfatigue, reduced muscle volume, diminished shock absorption, and, consequently, increased bone stress. Specific mistakes contributing to the feeling of fatigue include: an overly intense start to training without proper warm-up — 27%; excessive overall load due to a sharp increase in training duration — 10%; training muscles at high intensity — 8%; and engaging in large volumes of running without systematic preparation — 6% [9]. Preventing injuries, illnesses, and accidents during physical education and sports training is one of the primary responsibilities of teachers, coaches, instructors, medical personnel, and school administrators. However, in practice, not everyone consistently fulfills this responsibility. Violations of organizational, technical, sanitary, and hygienic standards are additional causes of accidents among athletes. Injuries are most frequently observed in football, which is due both to the nature of the sport and its mass popularity. Goalkeepers, forwards, and midfielders are most susceptible to injuries. Goalkeepers are typically injured during collisions, while forwards tend to get injured during sprints, physical clashes, and falls. Thus, injuries most commonly occur in the hands, knees, and lower legs. These are typically fractures, skin abrasions, and contusions [10]. In track and field athletics, approximately 70% of all injuries are classified as severe. The most frequently injured areas are the lower limbs (50–65%), upper limbs (35–50%), and the skull and spine (15–20%). Serious injuries also commonly affect the knee, ankle, shoulder, elbow, and wrist joints (see table) [11; www.ski.ru].

Table

Distribution of sports by injury

Sports	Head	Body	Pelvis	Feet and hands	
				High	Bottom
Football	4,48	2,59	2,14	14,12	76,67
Hockey	18,84	5,29	3,51	24,13	49,23
Wrestling	12,58	18,99	1,08	38,62	28,73
Boxing	23,89	4,15	0,33	51,56	20,07
Gymnastics	2,23	7,83	1,39	54,49	33,96
Athletics	2,17	4,56	1,98	23,88	67,41
Cyclist	13,54	7,09	1,93	34,85	42,59
Skier	11,79	2,71	1,38	18,74	65,28
Rowing	17,76	4,44	-	42,18	35,62
Swimmer	9,92	7,21	0,9	31,98	49,99

Surveys conducted among large groups (over 100 individuals) of athletes specializing in team sports (such as football, basketball) and martial arts (such as freestyle wrestling) at specialized sports schools revealed that due to sport-related illnesses and injuries, athletes were forced to miss between 7% to 45% of their training sessions and 5% to 35% of their competitive games [12].

Many well-known athletes are often compelled to devote more time and attention to treating illnesses and injuries than to actual training and physical activity. Some of them have had to undergo multiple complex surgeries and spend extended periods on rehabilitation. For prominent athletes specializing in popular sports such as boxing, tennis, football, basketball, and various types of wrestling, their sports careers are characterized by an ongoing cycle of intensive training, competitions, and injuries [9].

DISCUSSION. Based on performance indicators of sports schools and observations of athletes' activities, it is essential to enhance workplace safety by identifying the sources and causes of harmful and dangerous injury-inducing factors. Since the primary task of management is to ensure safety, working conditions are closely linked to this goal. On this basis, regulatory standards and sanitary-hygienic recommendations must be developed.

Main causes of injury include:

- Organizational shortcomings in conducting training sessions: This includes poorly structured training, conducting sessions without a coach, lack of discipline, and the use of defective or worn-out equipment.

- Neglect during the preparatory phase of training: Common issues include skipping warm-ups, improper instruction in exercise techniques, improper use of protective and self-protective equipment, forced overloading, and misapplication of methods and training tools.

- Insufficient material-technical support and lack of equipment: This involves poorly prepared training grounds, loosely fastened or unstable equipment, small and cramped sports halls [9], absence of safety zones, hard surfaces, and uneven paths.

- Unsatisfactory sanitary and hygienic conditions of halls and sports grounds: These may include poor ventilation, inadequate lighting of training areas, excessive dust, low air and pool water temperatures.

- Adverse meteorological conditions: Such as rain, snow, strong winds, and similar environmental factors.

- Inadequate educational discipline: This encompasses low levels of educational effort, violation of rules, recklessness, and inattentiveness on the part of both teachers and students.

- Lack of medical supervision: This includes admitting students to competitions without prior medical examination, neglecting the recovery period after illness, failure to limit training loads, and ignoring medical advice on assigning students to training groups based on their health and fitness levels.

CONCLUSION. As seen from the above, the root causes of injuries and accidents are often violations of mandatory safety rules during physical education sessions and training processes within educational institutions. The fight against injuries and health risks must be based on the strict adherence to these standards by physical education teachers, coaches, and students alike.

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